

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Let's dream a 'zero bombing philosophy' in the planet, let's shout and establish a peace surviving technique in the planet

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Defence and Law Research Centre, RMIT University, Australia
Textile, Color, and Material Research Centre; RMIT University, Australia
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia
engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au

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Keynote

Technologies of bombing may destroy may hamper the general surviving philosophy in the planet.

Keywords: bombing, peace.

Outcomes

- ✓ Every bombing should have a judicial explanation against the judicial crimes and criminals; without which every bomber should pay the judicial compensation should pay the judicial penalty to satisfy the global community; without which bomber should also take should also fund to re-build the country to re-build the nation to re-build the infrastructure to re-build the peace of the community.
- ✓ United Nations and countries should do practice of bombing authorization policy for having the judicial transparency for having the judicial assessment against crimes and criminals.
- ✓ Every invention of bombing technology should be registered at the office of United Nations if United Nations is judicially performing for peace surviving technique under the department of 'peace and security'.
- ✓ Every country should follow the existing policy of international court to keep a transparent record to satisfy the judicial arguments of compensations, history of crimes, criminals, and bombings.
- ✓ No global competition, no power, and no weapon should violate the peace surviving philosophy in the planet.

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Research Questions

1. How can global war be eliminated to influence peace survival techniques?
2. How can 'zero bombing philosophy' be established in the planet?
3. How can standard bombing policy be implemented against the crimes and criminals?
4. How can weapon competition and power be eliminated to influence peace survival techniques?

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Discussion

Every process of defence, safety, and war is an expensive phenomenon. Every war increases the total administrative costs of the country. Every bombing and fighting may increase the currency inflation of the country. Every citizen or member contributes and sacrifices the unit costs for the total administrative costs of the association of the country. Every president of the country is judicially liable to eliminate currency inflation and administrative costs of the country. Competitive currency inflation and administrative costs are also the performance of a president or prime minister or a political leader of a country during his/her time of leading. Every citizen and administrative leaders should judicially take care the bombing and fighting policy. Hence, bombing is not only killing the life, bombing is harming the wealth and planet, bombing is not environment-friendly for the global surviving in the planet. The research and development philosophy of bombing may be globally scrutinized and reduced. Let's stop the fighting and bombing. Let's stop the philosophy of global war for living as unit of human beings. Let's practice, establish, and contribute for a peace surviving technique in the planet. Let's invest in the research and development of peace surviving technique in the planet if people can dream a 'zero bombing philosophy' in the planet if people can try, focus, and establish a 'non-bloody philosophy' in the planet. Let's invest to record to analyze to eliminate the reason and season of bombing and fighting. Without which, there is possibility of atomic bombing; there is possibility of global fighting and global destruction. By nature, every person wants peace and peace. By nature, every person senses to respect the safety for the peace surviving technique. People are also afraid who have no research of weapon who have minimum research of bombing who can not invest for research and development philosophy of bombing who can not protect them-self against bombing who can not survive by managing the food of stomach who can not self-ensure a minimum quality of life due to numerous limitations[1-7].

To whom it may concern

A copy of this article was forwarded to the United Nations to circulate to the presidents of the nations to the judicial, administrative, and defence offices of the nations to improve to extend to invest to judge to moderate to consider for the global surviving philosophy in the planet rather than

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Chartered Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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the global destructive competition of weapon and power. Referred to daily newspaper on 28 February-6 March 2026, it was the time of the bombing and fighting between Iran, and Israil-United States of America when Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.); Barrister (Dr.) was worried about the global destructive philosophy about the global destructive competition of weapons and power[2].

Legal authorization and signing

 6 March 2026
 (Md. Anowar Hossain)
 Signature (scanned)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.); Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc & PhD in Applied Law; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, and BSc Engineering in Textile Technology

Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) since 1986

- <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
- <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
- <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
- www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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